

Deliverable Report D6.4

Outreach and Training Plan

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AO	Adverse Outcome
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
CA	Consortium Agreement
CRO	Contract Research Organization
CSO	Customer Service and Operations
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemistry Agency
ECHA-RAC	European Chemical Agency Committee for Risk Assessment
ECHA-SEAC	European Chemical Agency Committee for Socio-Economic Analysis
EFSA-PPR	European Food Safety Authority Plant Protection Products and their Residues
EP	Exploitation Plan
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KE	Key Event
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OECD -ESCA	Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development Emerging Science in Chemical Assessment
PARERE	Preliminary Assessment of Regulatory Relevance
PC	Project Coordinator
PCP	Project Communication Plan
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The aim of INSIGHT deliverable 6.4 (D6.4) is to present the outreach and training activities that the consortium intends to carry out during the project to spread knowledge and contribute to disseminating and exploiting the project results.

The document outlines the strategy and target groups of the training activities within the project, indicating methodologies and tools the consortium intends to use and pointing out the partners in charge of delivering INSIGHT training activities.

The training activities will provide novel competencies within academic, professional, and industrial domains, targeting potential users of the INSIGHT tools for Safe and Sustainability by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials. Training of young researchers as well as workshops for industry and regulatory bodies will be conducted.

The deliverable is structured in 5 chapters:

- Chapter 1 provides a short introduction to the INSIGHT project and the aim of the present deliverable.
- Chapter 2 briefly provides the consortium outreach and training strategy.
- Chapter 3 contains information on the planned INSIGHT International School
- Chapter 4 shows the INSIGHT workshop programs and objectives.
- Chapter 5 draft the organisation plan for the webinars targeting future industrial end users.
- Chapter 6 describes the supporting coordination activities of the dissemination partners

1 Introduction

1.1 INSIGHT in a Nutshell

Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) chemicals and materials are essential to address the challenges of modern society. However, lack of stakeholders' coordination, limited access to relevant data, and absence of standardised methods continue to hamper the development of a comprehensive approach to enable operationalisation of (the principles of) SSbD. INSIGHT will overcome these challenges by developing an innovative framework for mechanistic in silico impact assessment of chemicals and materials, through application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning approaches. The INSIGHT framework comprises a multi-layered approach that integrates data, models, and impact outcome pathway (IOP) knowledge graphs to enable identification of chemicals and materials properties driving specific biological effects to enable re-design and/or mitigation measures. INSIGHT will also provide curated and user-friendly Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) data and computational models and workflows. INSIGHT's outputs will support a paradigm shift in the in silico assessment of the sustainability and safety of chemicals and materials, from the current fragmented situation to a holistic and integrated approach. INSIGHT will provide decision maps as a part of its integrated framework to guide users through the decision-making process (including the computational algorithms and their applicability domains via an explainable AI approach), helping users to evaluate the social, economic, health and environmental impacts of (their) chemicals and materials in a more efficient and comprehensive manner. All of the INSIGHT tools and approaches will be presented via user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) with step-by-step guidance to circumvent the need for users to have programming skills themselves, thereby democratising access to state-of-the-art AI approaches.

The INSIGHT project is fully aligned with the EU principles of safety and sustainability³ and the European Green Deal.⁴ It supports the development of policies in the areas of environmental and biodiversity protection, public health, critical materials, and the circular economy for a dynamic commercial future that respects the planet by avoiding harm to humans and the environment.

By democratising the use of cutting-edge AI methods to SSbD, INSIGHT will drive innovation towards a digital, circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable economy. INSIGHT will help the industry to optimise the development and production of chemicals/materials and derived products, support regulators and policymakers in informed decision-making towards a safer and more sustainable society, and pave the way for a comprehensive approach to SSbD.

1.2 Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

This deliverable summarises the training and dissemination activities within the INSIGHT project and defines an accurate and comprehensive work plan for their implementation.

The Outreach and Training plan represents the strategic vision of the Consortium in view of sharing and therefore exploiting the open knowledge gathered and generated within the project, both by the scientific community and by professionals in diverse industrial and regulatory sectors. INSIGHT

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32022H2510>

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

workshops and webinars with external stakeholders and potential future end users are key activities for the validation of the developed method and framework.

The training activities will provide a pathway to the dissemination and therefore exploitation of the project results, raising awareness and providing novel competencies in application of the INSIGHT approaches to the current and next generation of scientists and professionals.

An effective implementation strategy for the INSIGHT training organisations is essential to ensure that INSIGHT project results are properly focused to the needs of the targeted audience.

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2 Outreach and Training Strategy

Training activities will focus to the professional development of young scientists and providing access and training to INSIGHT's models / tools to other practitioners, end-users, and other interested parties via training events showcasing methodological advances and new project outcomes.

Training actions target people inside (internal training) and outside (external training) the INSIGHT consortium. They are vital activities to train and educate a new generation of researchers across academia and industry and to widely disseminate relevant project outcomes and findings. Thus, internal and external training actions will be conducted during the four-year duration of the project. Training will be provided by and for personnel working on the project and by expert invited speakers. In parallel, workshops with external stakeholders will collect and integrate their feedback on the useability and utility of INSIGHT tools and methods to further iterate and improve the outputs and the associated training materials. These workshops are essential for the development and refinement of the INSIGHT Framework Graphical User Interface in WP5.

INSIGHT outreach and training activities will be tailored to each of the following target audiences:

- Researchers both experimental and computational, as the tools should also guide design and synthesis of new chemicals and materials;
- Key staff / Technical staff, to enable widespread implementation of INSIGHT's approaches;
- Research managers to raise awareness of the importance of embedding these approaches into laboratory workflows;
- Industrial executives responsible for regulatory compliance and sustainability;
- Regulatory experts who are responsible for the evaluation of chemicals and materials dossiers;
- Potential users of the tools and framework from all of the above categories.

Two training approaches have been confirmed:

- Organization of the INSIGHT International School for high-degree students, young researchers (both academia and enterprises), and professionals with a well-defined focus on INSIGHT-related disciplines
- Staff exchange between partner institutions, especially of young researchers. This includes, in particular, personnel exchange between involved academic and research institutes and enterprises; this will facilitate the extensive transfer of knowledge and technology transfer at later stages and possibly open job opportunities for young trained students (PhD, post-docs) in industry as well as enabling networking opportunities.

Moreover, other training activities useful to implement the identified strategy have been adopted:

- Seminars and lectures in relevant academic courses such as Materials Week, Venice Nanoschool etc
- Professional training via short courses / targeted sessions on the tools, e.g., at trade shows;
- Masters Theses aligned with the INSIGHT project activities (academic partners mainly).

3 INISIGHT International Schools

The INSIGHT International School is planned to be hosted by NovaM with support from UoB (to be confirmed). The school is addressed to Early-Stage Researchers (post-graduate, PhD students, and young post-docs) within and outside the INSIGHT project.

Organiser and Contributors: TAU, NTUA, NovaM, MUI, ULEI, UoB

Tentative Title: INSIGHT integrated framework for *in silico* impact assessment (of chemicals and materials)

Scope and Objectives:

The INSIGHT school program aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the latest *in silico* methodologies and tools used in assessing the impacts of chemicals and materials.

Objectives:

- Introduce participants to cheminformatics tools and techniques and the SSbD framework
- Explain the role of biological descriptors in evaluating chemical/material toxicity
- Teach participants to perform basic Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for chemicals, focusing on early-stage assessment
- Review regulatory frameworks for chemical/material safety and social/environmental impact assessment, and how these are addressed via the INSIGHT SSbD framework.

Preliminary Program:

Introduction to the INSIGHT integrated strategy for *in silico* impact assessment of chemicals and materials and the SSbD framework it aims to operationalise.

Participants will learn about the components and interactions of the INSIGHT framework for *in silico* impact assessment, particularly:

- Cheminformatic approaches for chemical/material impact assessment:
The session will cover the fundamentals of cheminformatics for predicting chemical/material properties and biological activities. A key focus will be on chemical descriptors, which are numerical values or fingerprints that capture essential chemical/material information such as molecular size, shape, and topological properties that can be derived automatically through electronic representations of molecules. Additionally, the session will delve into the application of machine learning techniques in cheminformatics. Students will learn how to use machine learning algorithms to analyse chemical/material data, build predictive models, and improve the accuracy of chemical/material impact assessments. Practical exercises will provide hands-on experience in utilising cheminformatics software including the Jqpot⁵ and Enalos⁶ cloud platforms
- Biological descriptors and toxicogenomics for chemical/material safety assessment:
Participants will learn how to use advanced analytical pipelines for OMICs data analysis and mechanistic characterization of chemical/material safety through an adverse outcome pathway (AOP). Hands-on session on the BMDx tool⁷ for dose-dependent analysis of transcriptomic data and the AOP Fingerprint tool⁸ for their mechanistic characterization. The combination of these two tools will aid the user in identifying dose-dependent genes following chemical exposure and mapping these genes to potential key events (KEs) and AOPs, ultimately linking molecular-level changes to adverse outcomes (AOs)

⁵ <https://app.jqpot.org/>

⁶ <https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/>

⁷ Serra et al., *Bioinformatics*, 2020, 36: 2932–2933, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa030>.

⁸ Saarimäki et al., *Advanced Science*, 2023, 10.2: 2203984, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202203984>

- **Life Cycle Assessment:**
Introduction to LCA, with a focus on the ex-ante assessment of novel and emerging chemical substances and materials. The session focuses on probabilistic approaches and the connection of LCA with other methods and tools in the SSbD toolbox. Trade-offs across the environmental, economic and social aspects of LCA will be addressed in a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) context.
- **Regulatory aspects for chemical safety and societal/environmental impact assessment:**
The session will provide an introduction to the traditional regulatory chemical safety assessment principles as well as the evolving concepts for Non-Animal-Methods (NAM) based Next-Generation-Risk-Assessment (NGRA) and the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) assessment strategy covering societal and environmental impacts more broadly. The practical limitations and uncertainties for the traditional and new approaches as well as the science and policy drivers for this ongoing evolution will be illuminated. Using the case-studies developed within INSIGHT the participants will receive hands-on training for the employment of the new INSIGHT decision maps. The latter will become available as new INSIGHT tools with the purpose to support regulatory decision making. The training will incorporate experience from the INSIGHT stakeholder workshops (see section 4).

4 INSIGHT Workshops

Within the INSIGHT project, two workshops will be organized in month 36 and 48 respectively, as deliverables D5.4 and D5.5

Hereafter a detailed description of each workshop.

I. Workshop M36

Scope and Objectives: Demonstrate INSIGHT decision map for an integrated Safe and Sustainable by Design assessment to inform stakeholders on the new science based regulatory options and collect their stakeholder feedback for the improvement of the decision map.

Tentative Title: INSIGHT decision maps 0.9 for an integrated *in silico* SSbD assessment

Target audience: Regulators from regulatory agencies and industry, regulatory experts from non-governmental organizations: EURL ECVAM Network for Preliminary Assessment of Regulatory Relevance (PARERE), European Food Safety Authority Plant Protection Products and their Residues (EFSA-PPR) panel & EFSA scientific committee, European Chemical Agency Committee for Risk Assessment (ECHA-RAC), European Chemical Agency Committee for Socio-Economic Analysis (ECHA-SEAC), Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development Emerging Science in Chemical Assessment advisory group (OECD -ESCA)

Partner in charge of the event and contributors: MUI, EMPA, TAU, MUI, NovaM, UoB

Location: Online

Preliminary program: (total of 4 hours work + ½ hour break)

Content	Time	Hour	Who
Basis and concept for Next Generation Risk Assessment 0.9 implemented in INSIGHT	15 min presentation + 5 minutes discussion	12:30 – 12:50	MUI
Basis and concept for Life Cycle Assessment as implemented in INSIGHT	15 min presentation + 5 minutes discussion	12:50 – 13:10	EMPA
Introduction to the IOP concept	30 min presentation + 10 min discussion	13:10 – 13:50	TAU
Presentation of the INSIGHT decision map using the first INSIGHT case studies	30 min presentation + 10 min discussion	13:50 – 14:30	MUI
Break	15 min	14:30 – 14:45	
Presentation of the graphical use interface for the decision maps	10 min presentation + 5 min discussion	14:45 - 15:00	NovaM, UoB
Participants testing the decision map using INSIGHT data from the second INSIGHT case study (or any simplified, modified version thereof)	20 min	15:00 – 15:20	participants

Q&A session on the exercise	10 min	15:20 – 15:30	TAU, MUI, NovaM
Continue testing the decision map	15 min	15:30 – 15:50	participants
Break	15 min	15:45-16:00	
Presentation & feedback from participants	30 min	16:00 – 16:30	participants
Wrap-up and conclusions	30 min	16:30 – 17:00	TAU, MUI, NovaM

2. Workshop M48

Scope and Objectives: Demonstrate the INSIGHT decision map for an integrated Safe and Sustainable by Design assessment to inform stakeholders on the new science-based regulatory options and collect their stakeholder feedback for the improvement of the decision map

Tentative Title: INSIGHT decision maps v. 1.0 for an integrated SSbD assessment

Target audience: Regulators/Risk Assessors from regulatory agencies and industry, regulatory experts from non-governmental organizations: PARERE, EFSA-PPR panel & EFSA scientific committee, ECHA-RAC, ECHA-SEAC, OECD –ESCA)

Partner in charge of the event and contributors: MUI, EMPA, TAU, NovaM, UoB

Location: online

Preliminary program:

Content	Time	Hour	Who
Updates on OECD & stakeholder input for Next Generation Risk Assessment 1.0 implemented in INSIGHT	15 min presentation + 5 minutes discussion	12:30 – 12:50	MUI
Updates on OECD & stakeholder input on Life Cycle Assessment 1.0 as implemented in INSIGHT	15 min presentation + 5 minutes discussion	12:50 – 13:10	EMPA
Updates on OECD & stakeholder input on the IOP concept	30 min presentation + 10 min discussion	13:10 – 13:50	TAU
Presentation of the INSIGHT decision map using the updated first INSIGHT case studies	30 min presentation + 10 min discussion	13:50 – 14:30	MUI
Break	15 min	14:30 – 14:45	
Presentation of the updated graphical user interface (GUI) for the decision maps	10 min presentation + 5 min discussion	14:45 - 15:00	NovaM, UoB
Participants testing the updated decision map using INSIGHT data from the second	20 min	15:00 – 15:20	participants

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INSIGHT case study (or any simplified, modified version thereof)			
Q&A session on the exercise	10 min	15:20 – 15:30	TAU, MUI, NovaM
Continue testing the updated decision map	15 min	15:30 – 15:50	participants
Break	15 min	15:45-16:00	
Presentation & feedback from participants	30 min	16:00 – 16:30	participants
Wrap up and conclusions	30 min	16:30 – 17:00	TAU, MUI, NovaM

Other Workshops

INSIGHT will also conduct 1-day workshops on FAIRification, data integration, impact assessment, and the INSIGHT framework will be organized, in collaboration with the Early Career Research group, in concomitance with the annual consortium meeting and project final event.

Scope and Objectives: inform and discuss FAIRification, data integration, impact assessment, and the INSIGHT framework.

Target audience students, early-career researchers, and industrial end-users

Partner in charge of the event and contributors: hosting partner, in collaboration with the relevant partners with expertise on the workshop topics and the whole consortium

Location: Online and in person, in conjunction with the annual consortium meetings and project final event.

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5 INSIGHT Webinars

Two webinars targeting industry will be organized by INSIGHT. The first webinar will be held at M20 (between August and September 2025). The second webinar will be held at M40 (April 2027).

Scope and Objectives: inform industry researchers and risk assessors about INSIGHT's impact assessment tools and gather feedback to ensure that INSIGHT's decision support tools and *in silico* framework outcomes meet industry needs.

Target audience: industry researchers and risk assessors

Partner in charge of the event and contributors: NovaM, in collaboration with all the industrial partners within the consortium.

Suggested topics/titles for webinars:

1. Isalos Analytics Platform: A Zero-Code Platform for Cheminformatics Analysis
2. Easy-MODA: Simplifying Standardized Registration of Scientific Simulation Workflows through MODA Template Guidelines powered by the Enalos Cloud Platform
3. Enalos Asclepios: Facilitating High Throughput Automated Molecular Docking and Dynamics for the Risk Assessment of Chemicals
4. Social LCA and its integration into sustainability assessment.
5. FAIR data management to support chemical and materials risk assessment.
6. Impact Outcome Pathways - a progression from AOPs to consider also impacts.

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6 Timelines for Promotion of Activities and Support from the Dissemination Partners

While the organisation of the technical content of training events, workshops, webinars and School is the responsibility of the named partners, the overall delivery of the program of events from an organisational and operational viewpoint, is with the dissemination partners (WH and AIST). A summary of the key steps that the dissemination partners will undertake is presented below, as pre-event, during the event and post-event activities, with a focus on the stakeholder management and dissemination.

Pre-event activities:

- **Preliminary Announcement:** a "save the date" notification will be distributed to the relevant target groups to inform them of the upcoming event.
- **Registration Form:** a registration form will be prepared, which includes GDPR compliance and permissions for recording or photographing during the event. This form will be distributed to attendees.
- **Content Collection:** a dedicated folder will be established to gather all necessary content related to the event.
- **Content Organization:** dedicated calls will be made to coordinate content and timings with subject matter experts to ensure a well-structured agenda.
- **Promotion:** LinkedIn posts and other promotional materials will be created and shared to generate interest in the event.
- **Pre-event Materials:** any materials required before the event will be distributed to participants to prepare them adequately.
- **Technical Support:** participants will be assisted in ensuring they have the necessary accounts or software installed before the event.
- **Platform Setup:** Teams or webinar platform will be configured, including options for recording the session.

During the event activities:

- **Logistical Support:** assistance will be provided with logistical elements such as admitting attendees, starting the recording, managing live captions, and organizing breakout rooms.
- **Documentation:** screenshots of attendee lists and pictures will be taken for social media and promotional purposes.
- **Live Updates:** real-time updates will be posted on LinkedIn during the event to engage with the audience and provide live insights.

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Post Event activities:

- **Feedback Distribution:** evaluation forms tailored to the specific event will be distributed to participants to gather feedback on their experience.
- **Stakeholder Follow-up and Relationship building:** the main objective of this activity is to reach out to attendees and speakers to gather additional feedback and explore collaboration opportunities; maintain ongoing communication with stakeholders and keep them informed about future events and initiatives and identify potential partnerships and sponsorship opportunities based on stakeholder engagement and feedback.
- **Certificates of Attendance:** certificates will be generated and distributed to attendees.
- **Recording Editing:** the recordings of the event will be edited, and all relevant materials will be compiled for the INSIGHT website and Zenodo platform where applicable.
- **Event Summary Preparation:** a summary of the event will be prepared for publication on the website and social media channels.

This structured approach ensures that all aspects of the event are managed effectively, enhancing stakeholder engagement and maximizing the impact of the dissemination efforts.

